

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EMOTIONAL CHANGES IN PEDIATRIC PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract. *The aim of the study was to identify psycho-emotional disturbances in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus at the early stages of the disease. A total of 205 children aged 7 to 18 years with type 1 diabetes mellitus were examined. The assessment included: a neurological examination with detailed analysis of questionnaire data and medical history clarification; evaluation of carbohydrate metabolism control indicators in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes; and, in order to objectify affective disorders, assessment of state and trait anxiety levels using the Spielberger–Khanin anxiety inventory. According to state and trait anxiety assessments, regardless of the disease duration, the findings were as follows: moderate state anxiety was observed in 58.5% of patients, and high state anxiety in 41.4%. Low levels of trait anxiety were recorded in 2% of patients, moderate levels in 34%, and high levels in 64%.*

Keywords: *genetic factors, structural and functional abnormalities,*

Introduction. The development of type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is believed to be caused by autoimmune disintegration of pancreatic beta cells. The autoimmune destruction of beta cells is, in turn, associated with a number of genetic factors and the influence of still poorly understood environmental triggers. According to numerous authors, this type of diabetes typically develops during childhood or adolescence and, in recent years, has consistently ranked among the most prevalent chronic non-communicable diseases [14]. According to statistical data, the number of people with diabetes worldwide doubles approximately every ten years. As a result, the number of complications arising from the disease also increases, which in turn leads to higher rates of early disability and premature mortality [8].

Among the wide range of complications associated with diabetes in children and adolescents, brain-related abnormalities take a primary and particularly important place. These often manifest as changes in cognitive and emotional functioning. Over the past several years, numerous studies have confirmed both direct and indirect effects of diabetes on structural and functional abnormalities in the brain [12]. According to various researchers, (1) the onset of diabetes at an early age has a significantly negative impact on the developing and not yet fully formed brain of a child, and (2) diabetes and its complications are unequivocally considered to be contributing factors in the development of both transient and persistent disturbances in emotional regulation and cognitive function due to acute or chronic decompensation of carbohydrate metabolism. It is important to note that, in our view, chronic hyperglycemia or hypoglycemia should be considered key triggers in the development of such disorders. As repeatedly noted in the literature, even if optimal glycemic targets are achieved, the pathological processes that have

already begun in the brain may be irreversible. While their progression can be slowed, their manifestations reduced, and—under proper correction—their parameters brought closer to age norms, complete resolution is currently considered unattainable [1].

As previously noted, in addition to cognitive impairments, changes in the emotional-volitional domain are considered core manifestations of cerebral dysfunction in pediatric patients with diabetes. The frequency of emotional disturbances in T1DM is several times higher than in the general population, and twice as common in girls as in boys [16]. These psycho-emotional disorders can vary widely in severity, ranging from mild conditions to severe impairments approaching clinical psychiatric disorders. It should be emphasized that this gradation is largely conditional, as even mild disturbances—though seemingly inconspicuous—can be clinically significant, especially when combined with other chronic complications.

The most commonly observed emotional disturbance in children and adolescents with T1DM is an increased level of anxiety. In neurology, anxiety is understood as a persistent predisposition to experience worry, with diverse clinical features. According to many authors, anxiety disorders are reversible and typically characterized by an unjustified and destabilizing sense of fear, nervousness, and restlessness, often arising without any clear external cause [4,11].

Numerous studies focusing on the psychological adaptation of children with T1DM emphasize a steady increase in trait anxiety (TA) and state anxiety (SA). Statistical data show that the prevalence of anxiety in children and adolescents with T1DM ranges from 15% to 42%. Elevated anxiety levels in this population are primarily associated with the nature of the disease itself: the constant need for injections and self-monitoring. Additionally, the overprotectiveness of parents, who often assume the role of a controlling authority, contributes to this condition. According to C.D. Spielberger, high levels of trait anxiety are characterized by a persistent tendency to interpret a broad spectrum of situations as threatening, which in turn results in heightened anxiety responses. State anxiety is marked by situational tension, restlessness, and nervousness.

It becomes clear that such abnormalities not only impair the social adaptation of children with T1DM but also negatively affect the course and outcome of the disease [3,13]. At present, a wide variety of approaches for assessing emotional and volitional functioning are available. Most are based on recreating simple psychological constructs during the assessment, in which the subject must position their own reactions—either verbally or through projective methods. Due to their simplicity in both implementation and analysis, verbal techniques are the most widely used. However, despite the numerous positive reviews of these methods, they have significant drawbacks. The main limitations include subjectivity and insufficient sensitivity, since the subject's responses may be influenced by various exogenous factors (e.g., fatigue, educational level), which can naturally distort the final results [9].

In conclusion, the study of the emotional-volitional sphere in pediatric patients with T1DM remains highly relevant, as such disturbances are widespread and play a significant role in determining the rehabilitation potential of these patients.

Objective

To identify psycho-emotional disturbances in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) at the early stages of the disease.

Materials and Methods. A total of 205 children aged 7 to 18 years with T1DM were included in the study. Of these, 81 children (39.5%) were aged 7 to 11 years (mean age: 9.0 ± 1.6 years), and 124 children (60.5%) were aged 12 to 18 years (mean age: 14.7 ± 1.8 years). According

to the study protocol, all patients underwent a comprehensive clinical and neurological examination, including a detailed review of questionnaire responses and clarification of medical history. Glycemic control indicators in children and adolescents with T1DM were assessed based on the recommendations of the American Diabetes Association (ADA) and International Society for Pediatric and Adolescent Diabetes (ISPAD) [10]. According to these guidelines:

- Optimal glycemic control: HbA1c < 7.0%
- Suboptimal control: HbA1c 7.6% to 9.0%
- High risk: HbA1c > 9.0%

To objectively assess affective disorders, the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) developed by C.D. Spielberger and Y.L. Khanin was used.

- Trait anxiety (TA) refers to a relatively stable individual characteristic reflecting the tendency to perceive a wide range of situations as threatening and to respond to them with varying levels of anxiety.

- State anxiety (SA) reflects a momentary adaptive response to a stressful or frustrating situation.

Scores below 30 are considered low anxiety, 31–45 as moderate anxiety, and above 45 as high anxiety [6].

Results and Discussion. Among the total of 205 patients examined:

- 81 patients (39.5%) were aged 7–11 years
- 124 patients (60.5%) were aged 12–18 years

Disease duration was distributed as follows:

- Less than 3 years: 78 patients (38%)
- 3 to 6 years: 67 patients (32.6%)
- More than 6 years: 60 patients (29.2%)

In the group with disease duration less than 3 years:

- 46 patients (56.8%) were aged 7–11
- 32 patients (25.8%) were aged 12–18

In the group with disease duration of 3 to 6 years:

- 23 patients (28.4%) were aged 7–11
- 44 patients (35.4%) were aged 12–18

In the group with disease duration over 6 years:

- 12 patients (14.8%) were aged 7–11
- 48 patients (38.7%) were aged 12–18

Onset of diabetes before age 7 in the group with disease duration less than 3 years was observed in 31 patients (30.7%), while 47 patients (45.2%) were diagnosed after age 7. In the 3–6-year duration group, T1DM was diagnosed before age 7 in 29 patients (28.7%), and after age 7 in 38 patients (36.5%).

In the group with the longest disease duration (more than 6 years), T1DM was diagnosed before age 7 in 41 patients (40.6%), and after age 7 in 19 patients (18.3%).

As shown in Table 1, when comparing disease duration by sex, no statistically significant differences were found ($P = 0.847$, Pearson's Chi-squared test). However, when analyzing disease duration based on the age at onset, statistically significant differences were revealed ($P = 0.002$, Pearson's Chi-squared test). According to the data obtained, a significant association was also established when comparing disease duration across age groups ($P < 0.001$, Pearson's Chi-squared test). Furthermore, analysis of disease duration in relation to glycemic control status showed

significant differences as well ($P = 0.016$, Pearson's Chi-squared test). These findings demonstrate that regardless of disease duration, most of the 205 patients were in a stage of decompensation. These results are consistent with previously published data in the literature. When comparing HbA1c levels based on disease duration, it was observed that during the first 1.5–2 years following the onset of type 1 diabetes (regardless of age), HbA1c values were significantly lower, with a mean of 8.4%. This phenomenon can be explained by the presence of residual endogenous insulin secretion during this early stage of the disease.

Table 1. Distribution of examined patients by age and sex at the time of T1DM onset, across groups with varying disease duration.

Groups	Gender		P	Debut		P	Age		P
	Boys	Girls		Up to 7 years	Above 7 years		(7-11)	(12-18)	
Up to 3 years	37 (40,2)	41 (36,3)	0,847	31 (30,7)	47 (45,2)	0,002*	46 (56,8)	32 (25,8)	<0,001*
3–6 years	29 (31,5)	38 (33,6)		29 (28,7)	38 (36,5)		23 (28,4)	44 (35,5)	
More than 6 year olds	26 (28,3)	34 (30,1)		41 (40,6)	19 (18,3)		12 (14,8)	48 (38,7)	

* – differences in statistically significant indicators ($P < 0,05$).

Table 2. Characteristics of carbohydrate metabolism indicators by disease duration (Me [Q1; Q3]) in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus

	Up to 3 years (n=78)	3–6 years (n=67)	More than 6 years (n=60)	P
Fasting glucose	8,4 [5,7; 9,1]	8,4 [6,3; 10,0]	8,6 [7,7; 9,5]	0,005* P more than 6 years – up to 3 years = 0,005
HbA1c (%)	8,4 [6,6; 10,3]	9,5 [7,5; 11,1]	10,4 [8,7; 11,8]	< 0,001* P 3-6 years – up to 3 years = 0,045 P more than 6 year – up to 3 years < 0,001

*- differences in statistically significant indicators ($p < 0,05$).

In the group with disease duration between **3 and 6 years**, specifically by the middle of the third year of type 1 diabetes (T1D), carbohydrate metabolism parameters showed a significant deterioration, with **mean HbA1c levels** significantly higher compared to those with a disease duration under 3 years — **9.5% ($p < 0.001$)**. In patients with a **disease duration over 6 years**,

the trend of HbA1c deterioration persisted, with average levels significantly higher — **10.4% (p < 0.001)** — than in groups with a shorter disease history. Additionally, children with more than 6 years of T1D had **significantly higher fasting plasma glucose** levels compared to those with a disease duration of less than 3 years.

Thus, based on the presented table, a **statistically significant difference** in HbA1c levels across different durations of T1D was identified (**p < 0.001**), using the **Kruskal–Wallis test**. Our findings indicate that **metabolic compensation levels are dependent on disease duration**: even if some degree of metabolic control is maintained in early stages due to residual insulin secretion, with longer disease duration, **the trend toward deterioration increases**, especially in the absence of adequate therapeutic attention.

According to the results of the **State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)** developed by **C.D. Spielberger and adapted by Y.L. Hanin**, regardless of disease duration, **moderate situational (state) anxiety** was observed in **120 (58.5%)** patients, while **high situational anxiety** was identified in **85 (41.4%)** children. As for **trait anxiety**, a **low level** was recorded in **4 (2%)** patients, **moderate** in **70 (34%)**, and **high** in **131 (64%)** of the participants. When analyzing anxiety levels **based on disease duration**, moderate **state anxiety** was detected in:

- **62.8%** of children with T1D duration < 3 years,
- **49.3%** of those with duration between 3 and 6 years,
- **63.3%** of those with duration > 6 years.

High **state anxiety** was present in:

- **37.2%** of patients with less than 3 years of disease,
- **50.7%** with 3–6 years,
- **36.7%** with over 6 years.

Regarding **trait anxiety**, a **moderate level** was found in:

- **37.2%** of patients with disease duration < 3 years,
- **28.4%** with 3–6 years,
- **36.7%** with > 6 years.

High trait anxiety was observed in:

- **60.3%**,
- **70.1%**,
- and **61.7%** of the respective groups (see Table 3).

When evaluating the State Anxiety Scale in relation to the duration of type 1 diabetes (T1D), no statistically significant differences were identified ($P = 0.171$; Pearson's chi-squared test). Similarly, when comparing the Trait Anxiety Scale based on disease duration, no statistically significant differences were observed ($P = 0.764$; Pearson's chi-squared test). Despite this, analysis of anxiety levels across different durations of disease revealed that subclinical anxiety disorders were already present during the early stages of T1D. As mentioned earlier, moderate trait anxiety (TA) was found in 37.2% of patients, while high trait anxiety was observed in 60.3% of cases. Regarding state anxiety (SA) at disease onset, moderate levels were identified in 49 (62.8%) children, and high levels in 29 (37.2%) patients.

One of the clinical features of T1D manifestation is the exacerbation of premorbid personality traits, which shapes an individual's response to the disease [2]. These reactions can manifest as heightened anxiety, excessive pedantic behavior in disease management, or, conversely, as an overly relaxed attitude toward the illness. Anxiety traits—both situational and

personal—were more pronounced in patients at the early stages of the disease than in those with 3 or more years of disease duration, which is regarded as a form of adaptation [5].

Table3. Level of situational and personal anxiety in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes according to the Spielberg-Khanin scale

Indicators		Duration of DM			P
		Up to 3 years n=78	3–6 years n=67	More than 6 years n=60	
Situational anxiety					
Low (<30 points)	Number of patients, %	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0)	0,171
Moderate (30 - 45)	Number of patients, %	49 (62,8)	33 (49,3)	38 (63,3)	
High (≥46 points)	Number of patients, %	29 (37,2)	34 (50,7)	22 (36,7)	
Personal anxiety					
Low (<30 points)	Number of patients, %	2 (2,6)	1 (1,5)	1 (1,7)	0,764
Moderate (30 - 45)	Number of patients, %	29 (37,2)	19 (28,4)	22 (36,7)	
High (≥46 points)	Number of patients, %	47 (60,3)	47 (70,1)	37 (61,7)	

* – differences in statistically significant indicators (P <0,05).

However, in our study, it was noted that while the frequency of moderate emotional disturbances decreased during the mid-stage of the disease (3–6 years), it increased again in patients with longer disease duration (>6 years). This supports the biphasic model of emotional response development, as described by several researchers—namely, a peak at disease onset and another during the complications phase. Furthermore, this pattern may reflect dysfunction in the limbic-reticular complex, basal ganglia, and secondary dysfunction of the frontal lobes, which is often associated with the emergence of the so-called “disconnection syndrome.”

In studies conducted by N.N. Yahno and V.V. Zakharov (2002), it was noted that emotional disturbances in the later stages of chronic diseases can be linked to secondary dysfunction of the frontal lobes. This is due to the critical role of connections between the anterolateral frontal cortex and the striatal system, which participate in maintaining positive emotional drive and goal-directed behavior [7].

In addition to elevated levels of state and trait anxiety, patients—particularly children and adolescents with T1D—also displayed behavioral abnormalities, which may be attributed to limbic system dysfunction. This symptom complex not only includes mnemonic (memory-related) and emotional impairments, but also various behavioral deviations resembling psychopathic features—such as histrionic traits, hypochondriasis, demonstrative or attention-seeking behavior, dishonesty, and in some cases, disturbances in instinctive behaviors including bulimia or aggressiveness [15].

The findings of this study enabled us to identify the following correlational relationships, as summarized in Table 4:

Table 4. Results of the correlation analysis between anxiety scales and HbA1c levels

Indicator	Characteristics of the correlation relationship		
	ρ	Chaddock's Tightness of Connection Scale	p
Situational Anxiety Scale	0,123	Low	0,078
Personal Anxiety Scale	0,204	Low	0,003*

* – differences in statistically significant indicators ($P < 0,05$).

Correlation between HbA1c and Anxiety Scales

A weak but positive correlation was found between HbA1c levels and the state anxiety scale. Specifically, an increase in HbA1c by 0.06% was associated with a 1-point increase in the state anxiety score. Similarly, a weak but positive correlation was observed between HbA1c and the trait anxiety scale, where an increase in HbA1c by 0.071% corresponded to a 1-point rise in the trait anxiety score. Thus, the correlation analysis between emotional disturbances—measured by the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) developed by C.D. Spielberger and Yu.L. Khanin—and glycemic control indicators demonstrated that higher HbA1c levels are associated with greater severity of anxiety symptoms.

Conclusions

The results obtained from the state and trait anxiety scales confirm the presence of psychoemotional disorders in patients with type 1 diabetes. These disorders manifest as a constitutional predisposition to persistent feelings of anxiety, fears, excessive worries, and negative emotions triggered by various internal or external factors. Such psychoemotional vulnerability may contribute to a more labile course of diabetes and, consequently, more pronounced impairment of the brain's nonspecific regulatory systems, particularly those within the limbic-reticular complex, which serve as the anatomical substrates of emotions. Therefore, an essential priority for healthcare professionals is the early identification and ongoing monitoring of the psychoemotional status in patients with type 1 diabetes, starting from the initial stages of the disease.

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